

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR FAILURE OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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Interlaminar shear crack propagation is a failure mechanism unique to the fiber reinforced composites. All applications of composite materials must take into account this potential fracture path and design procedures which contain adequate safety margins must be developed. As part of an overall research program into fracture criterion of composites the interlaminar shear (ILS) strength of hybrid materials of potential use in structural applications has been determined as a function of both fiber orientation and the material lay up. Both the base materials (graphite, glass and kevalar fibers in epoxy) and hybrid of these materials were tested in short beam shear to determine the absolute ILS strength and the effect of the hybrid interfaces on this parameter. The effect of residual stresses at, for example, the interface between the graphite and glass layers will be discussed in detail. The effect of the structure of the fracture path has been determined in detail by scanning microscopy. In addition to simple short beam shear tests, some ILS fatigue test were performed to determine the relative resistance of the different materials to dynamic environments introducing significant interlaminar shear stresses. These data will be described in detail.